

DATAWiSE: A Scalable Big Data Reference Architecture for Smart Buildings

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Abstract—The emergence of Digital Twin technology has dramatically changed operational and managerial practices in intelligent buildings by enabling real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and performance improvement. However, the management of large and heterogeneous data produced by Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, Building Information Models (BIM), and environmental systems poses a challenge in terms of interoperability, scalability, and real-time processing capability. This paper presents the DATAWiSE architecture, a modular and scalable big data framework that is designed to integrate disparate building data sources while ensuring both secure and efficient data management. A detailed account of the process followed, from user requirements collection to the design of the proposed reference architecture. The proposed multi-layered architecture combines distributed storage technologies, AI-based analytics, and standardized communication protocols to provide strong data governance while enabling informed decision-making. Explainable AI approaches also assist in increasing system transparency and stakeholder trust. Future development areas include further enhancements in federated learning, edge computing, and harmonization with international data-sharing protocols to increase the architecture's applicability within larger smart city infrastructures.

Index Terms—big data architecture, interoperability, building digital twin, AI-driven analytics, smart buildings

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement in digital technology is transforming many domains, especially in the domain of the built environment, recognized as being a major innovation represented in the form of a Digital Twin. A Digital Twin is a virtual twin to a real asset, system, or process, allowing real-time observation, simulation, and optimization across its entire lifecycle [1]. In smart buildings, Digital Twins enable efficient performance management, encourage preventive maintenance, and

enhance user experience as they combine and evaluate information drawn from multiple sources.

Intelligent structures incorporate multiple systems and appliances, some of them HVAC (heating, ventilation and air conditioning) systems, lighting control systems, security systems, and the Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, thus creating vast amounts of information in total [2]. Merging and managing this varied information is associated with major problems, such as interoperability problems, information silos, and highly scalable architectures, as well as real-time processing capacities for information. Successful solutions for problems are pivotal for achieving Digital Twin technology in smart buildings.

A multitude of research works have studied scalable architectural schemes for supporting the deployment of Digital Twins in smart building setups. In particular, a new software structure is introduced for creating and managing precise replicas relative to smart buildings and thus supporting the deployment of respective Digital Twins in smart cities [3]. Moreover, there are other research works that study different aspects related to IoT heterogeneity in buildings and stresses the need for integrated multiple-mode and automated engineering practices [4], [5]. The use of Building Information Models (BIM) in conjunction with semantic schemes like the BRICK schema [6] is identified as being vital for interoperability in Digital Twin frameworks [7].

Despite these advancements, there is still a need for a flexible and integrated system that is capable of addressing the unique demands that surround smart buildings. The system should be able to consolidate multiple sources of information, ensure interoperability, and enable real-time analysis to maximize the potential

TABLE I
EXISTING REFERENCE ARCHITECTURES

Reference Architecture	Scope	Features	Limitations
DIGIBUILD	Digital transformation of buildings, focusing on advanced analytics related to energy and performance monitoring, infrastructure management, and policy/finance support.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modular, layered design • Compliance with widely adopted standards • Scalable micro-services based approach • Focus on data integration, quality and secure sharing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple layers lead to complex integration • Complex and resource-intensive Data Lake
MATRYCS	Energy-efficiency in buildings focusing on big data analytics decision-making, infrastructure design and policy evaluation. Additionally, enables cross-sector data integration to support large-scale use cases for energy profiling and benchmarking across building portfolios.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three-layer architecture: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Governance: Data acquisition, curation, and storage. – Processing: Model development, evaluation, and serving. – Analytics: User-centric visualizations, digital twin, and toolbox. • Structured and extensible ontology with cross domain applicability. • Emphasizes privacy and regulatory compliance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heavy reliance on high-quality data. • Difficulty to maintain ontology with diverse data sources. • Complexity in integrating multiple heterogeneous data sources.
BD4NRG	Energy sector digitalization focusing on big data across energy value chains, using smart grid analytics, data-driven decision-making and a dynamic marketplace offering advanced interoperable services.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Layered approach including Data Sources, Data Interoperability, and Innovative Data Analytics Services layers. • Scalable and decentralized framework. • Emphasizes security with dynamic data access control, traceability, and confidentiality. • Marketplace model facilitating data and service exchange. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focuses on smart grids and energy data trading, lacking depth in fine-grained building analytics. • Complex integration due to highly heterogeneous data sources and stakeholders involved.
BRIDGE	Focuses on providing a common framework for data interoperability, business model validation and regulatory support, aiming to foster collaboration between industry stakeholders and policymakers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-layered architecture with clear separation between business logic and technical functions. • Supports data information exchange and cross-platform compatibility. • Policy recommendations and interoperability across domains. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides a general framework with limited specialized focus on advanced building-level analytics. • Requires customization and additional components.

of Digital Twin solutions [8].

This manuscript introduces a structure and a system for a big data system in a sustainable manner in line with the parameters of the DATAWiSE program, aimed at addressing the complexity involved in managing and integrating varied building information. The system in this paper employs state-of-the-art techniques and tools to exploit smart buildings based on Digital Twins to maximize efficiency and encourage sustainable performance.

The following chapters in this report are structured in a certain way. Section II presents background information on current problems and related solutions related

to data management systems; Section III presents the methodology used in creating the architecture; Section IV discusses use cases and requirements taken into account; Section V presents in detail an explanation of the suggested DATAWiSE Reference Architecture; and Section VI concludes the report summarizing findings and providing recommendations for future research work.

II. BACKGROUND

The building and energy sectors' digitalization have necessitated working in a big data environments with

multiple heterogeneous data sources, ranging from metered real-time data to static building metadata. This however bears significant challenges, particularly in terms of storage, processing, scaling and data analysis. Moreover, integrating such diverse data sources, while ensuring high level of quality and interoperability, poses its own challenges as it usually requires a complex and resource intensive system.

The proposed architecture aims to address these challenges and provide a robust, scalable and trustworthy foundation that can effectively support diverse data, advanced analytics and machine learning. The methodologies to be supported should be similar to those proposed in the book by Sarma et al. [9], focusing on Machine Learning approaches for optimal energy management in buildings. In order to design such a system, it is important to first evaluate existing frameworks and build upon their strengths and limitations. This will ensure that the final architecture aligns with best practices, while providing a suitable solution that combats the current limitations.

As an initial step, a set of EU projects with closely related objectives and features were identified and selected, in order to examine and analyze the reference architectures developed during their lifetime. This analysis ensures that previous experiences and lessons-learned in the same field are taken into account when designing the DATAWiSE architecture. The four projects selected were DigiBUILD [10], MATRYCS [11], BD4NRG [12] and BRIDGE [13], while the main selection criteria was their relevant scope and focus on bid data, data exchange and analytic services. The selection process additionally emphasized reference architectures that adhere to widely accepted architectural standards, such as layered, service-oriented or microservices-based, in order to promote modularity, reusability and adaptability. Thus, several EU initiatives that followed patterns that were less aligned – such as centralized and tightly coupled designs – had to be excluded. The results of their most related features and limitations are detailed in Table I.

In addition to examining and taking into account the strong points of these reference architectures, it is also important to incorporate widely adopted best practices and industry standards so as to ensure the creation of a strong and reliable foundation. Several established initiatives such as IDSA (International Data Spaces Association) [14], GAIA-X [15] and FIWARE [16], have set key principles that align with the scope and objectives of the proposed architecture. In addition to their relevance, these frameworks were selected for their widespread popularity and effectiveness across various industries.

These initiatives have been thoroughly analyzed and

several key principles and standards have been identified as necessary for the proposed architecture. This will ensure that the architecture aligns with current trends and best practices and provides a future-proof, flexible ecosystem. The core identified principles are the following:

- **Data Sovereignty and Security:** The architecture should enforce access policies and provide stakeholders with full control over their data, while maintaining compliance with legal and regulatory requirements.
- **Interoperability and Standardization:** The system should use standardized interfaces and communication protocols, to ensure seamless data exchange across different components.
- **Data Usage Policies:** Access and processing rights should be defined and enforced for all data sources.
- **Trusted Data Exchange:** Data exchange should be accompanied by security mechanisms, such as encryption, identity verification, and transaction logging.
- **Federated Identity and Access Management:** The architecture should include authentication mechanisms and identity federation, while also maintaining user privacy.
- **Scalability and Reliability:** The architecture should be designed to be scalable, with dynamic resource allocation in order to accommodate growing volumes of data and user traffic.

III. METHODOLOGY

The design of the DATAWiSE Scalable Big Data Architecture follows a structured framework aimed at aligning with project objectives and the expectations of the stakeholders. The framework includes a chain of sequential phases with the aim of developing a robust, flexible, and efficient architectural model.

- **Step 1-User requirements collection:** The first step in developing the architecture was the gathering of requirements from multiple stakeholders, including building operators, energy managers, facility managers, and researchers. This was done through workshops, surveys, and feedback sessions, thus ensuring that the architecture supports multiple operational needs and meets regulatory requirements.

- **Step 2-User requirements and use case analysis:** A comprehensive analysis of user requirements and use cases were conducted, combining insight drawn from co-creating processes such as stakeholder participation and the development of scenarios. The phase ensured that the architecture remains user-centric and aligns with realistic implementation within realistic environments.

- **Step 3-Functional and non-Functional requirements definition:** Following the use case analysis, the functional and non-functional requirements were defined. Functional requirements focused on data ingestion,

storage, processing, analytics, and reporting, while non-functional requirements emphasized scalability, performance, security, privacy, interoperability, and reliability.

- **Step 4-Architecture pattern selection:** Various architecture patterns were evaluated for their suitability in handling large-scale data processing, flexibility, and maintainability.

- **Step 5-Identification of software components:** Key software components essential to the architecture were identified and analyzed to ensure compatibility with the selected architecture pattern.

- **Step 6-Infrastructure selection:** The necessary infrastructure for supporting the architecture was selected based on scalability, performance, and integration capabilities.

- **Step 7-Reference Architecture design:** A comprehensive reference architecture was developed, including detailed diagrams and documentation to illustrate component interactions, data flow, and integration points.

This structured methodology guarantees that the DATAWiSE architecture is scalable, efficient, and secure, laying a solid foundation for future developments and deployments.

IV. FUNCTIONAL AND NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS DEFINITION

To design the DATAWiSE architecture in a manner that meets the diverse expectations of various stakeholders and provides a scalable and interoperable framework, a complete requirements analysis was conducted. This involved the identification of critical functions that are crucial to the operation of the system and the specification of primary quality attributes that are required to achieve long-term sustainability and flexibility. Functional requirements focus mainly on the inherent functions of the system that provide relevant inputs and outputs to end users and also consider prominent attributes and edge case instances. On the other hand, non-functional requirements play a critical role in specifying the quality metrics and main attributes of the system, such as the scaling, performance, maintainability, and compliance measures. These elements together form the foundation of a sound and future-proofed big data architecture designed to be deployed in Digital Twin applications in smart buildings. Phases one to three of the process of requirement identification are described and visualized in Figure 1. As shown, the successful identification of relevant requirements requires careful review and analysis of user requirements and service requirements through a disciplined and systematic process.

A. Functional Requirements

These define the core operations and services that the DATAWiSE architecture must support. The most

important functional requirements obtained from the requirement analysis are the following:

- **Data interoperability and integration:** Given the diversity of data sources, the architecture must support multiple data formats and ensure seamless integration with different external systems, including BIM models and IoT devices.
- **Data ingestion and collection:** Efficient data collection from various sources is essential for a Digital Twin system. The ability to process high-frequency data streams in real-time ensures accurate monitoring and optimization of building operations.
- **Data storage and management:** The architecture must handle both dynamic and static data from buildings, ensuring long-term storage and quick retrieval for analytics.
- **Data processing and analytics:** The system should support modular AI-driven services, enabling predictive maintenance, anomaly detection, and energy optimization to improve operational efficiency.
- **Security and access control:** Ensuring data security and access control is critical to maintaining stakeholder trust. Encryption and authentication mechanisms must be in place to safeguard sensitive information.
- **User-centric Interfaces:** A well-designed user interface and dashboards are crucial for facility managers, building owners, and researchers to make data-driven decisions efficiently.

B. Non-Functional requirements

Equally important to functional requirements, non-functional requirements define quality attributes and constraints that ensure system robustness and sustainability. The key non-functional requirements derived from the requirement analysis are the following:

- **Scalability:** As building data continues to grow, the architecture must be able to accommodate increasing data volumes and integrate new sources dynamically.
- **Performance:** Low-latency data processing is required to enable real-time decision-making, reducing energy consumption and improving building efficiency.
- **Reliability and availability:** The system must guarantee continuous operation with minimal downtime, integrating failover mechanisms to handle disruptions smoothly.
- **Maintainability:** A modular approach should be adopted, allowing components to be updated or replaced independently without impacting the overall system.
- **Compliance and governance:** Data management must align with regulatory frameworks, ensuring

Fig. 1. Overview of steps 1-7 for the requirements identification and the the architecture design process.

adherence to privacy laws such as GDPR and industry standards for secure data transactions.

This structured approach to defining functional and non-functional requirements ensures that the DATAWiSE architecture can effectively support Digital Twin applications while meeting the needs of diverse stakeholders.

V. THE DATAWiSE REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

The general visualization of the DATAWiSE reference architecture, including the different layers and the interaction between their components, is depicted in Figure 2. The definition of the DATAWiSE architecture represents the direct response to the non-functional and functional requirements outlined above. The design pro-

cess involves steps four to seven, which are depicted in Figure 1.

To address the functional and non-functional technical requirements identified in Step 3, a layered architecture was selected during Step 4 of the methodology—Architecture pattern selection. This design was chosen to meet the diverse needs of the system components by ensuring separation of concerns, modularity, and scalability. These layers are:

- **Data Input Layer:** Responsible for deploying and managing the various connectors to data sources, and for harmonizing incoming data to ensure consistency.
- **Data Infrastructure Layer:** Responsible for structuring, storing, and managing data.

- **Communication Layer:** Responsible for managing access to data, both within the ecosystem and externally.
- **Intelligence and Analytics Layer:** Responsible for utilizing building data to generate intelligent insights through services.
- **User Interaction Layer:** Responsible for deploying and managing user interfaces, and ensuring their connection to both the data and analytics services.

Along with the overall layered architectural design, additional decisions were required at a finer-grained level. To achieve data interoperability and integration, event-driven design was utilized, in which the connectors integrate disparate data sources and send data to a central data bus. Regarding data storage and management, a data lake approach was taken, using different database types to support different types of data: time series databases for temporal data, object storage for BIM files, and relational databases for static building data. For data processing and analytics, a microservices-based architecture was used to make the system more modular and extensible. This architectural approach makes the system easily adaptable to possible future changes.

The following part describes the architecture of DATAWiSE with a focus on its stratified design. Following sections include a detailed explanation of the reasoning behind the elements making up the architecture, driven by the overall goals of the system and current best practice in the field.

The *Data Input Layer* is the entry point for all building-related data and is responsible for ingesting heterogeneous data sources efficiently. It integrates static and dynamic datasets from BIM models, IoT sensors, environmental monitoring systems, and operational logs. The layer implements API gateways, data connectors, and ingestion pipelines to ensure a uniform data format before processing. The necessity of this layer lies within the intricacies of handling different sources of data with different formats, resolutions, and update ratio. The ingestion mechanism applies standard protocols such as RESTful APIs, messaging brokers, and BMS system data. Processing and structuring of the data at the point of initial intake enables the subsequent layers to ensure that they are receiving well-structured and reliable input by reducing the computing requirements of the subsequent phases. The layer also includes BIM data mining services, which extract geometric, semantic, and operational insights from building models, ensuring cross-compatibility between static and dynamic data sources.

For dynamic data, it will be built using message brokers to support event-driven processing, ensuring that real-time data streams are efficiently managed and distributed. For BIM data mining, an open IFC workflows

will be developed to ensure the mining of BIM data of good quality.

The *Data Infrastructure Layer* is responsible for handling operations involving the intake of the data, harmonization of the data, storing the data, and retrieving the data. The layer ensures that different types of data are integrated into a consistent and well-arranged repository that enables fast analytical processes. To cater for different types of datasets such as files, BIM data, and time series data, the layer uses distributed storage technologies. The implementation of the layer is prompted by the need for efficient data storage that enables fast query and analysis. The architecture follows the multi-model storage strategy that enables efficient storage and extraction of structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data.

The *Communication Layer* enables fast and secure data transfer within the system while simultaneously providing secure interoperability with external systems. The Communication Layer is critical for the enforcement of data sovereignty and for the development of collaborative data sharing with external environments. The Communication Layer includes federated identity management and role-based access control using OAuth2.0 [17] and Keycloak [18] for the restriction of sensitive building data for approved individuals and approved services. The Communication Layer applies semantic data fusion techniques that integrate different sources of data into context-enhanced datasets that enhance the quality of subsequent analysis.

The *Intelligence and Analytics Layer* transforms raw data into meaningful insights using machine learning, AI-driven analytics, and domain-specific models. The layer includes several AI services and assessment techniques such as:

- **Predictive Maintenance:** Uses deep learning models (LSTMs, Random Forests) to detect anomalies in building equipment.
- **Energy demand and generation forecasting:** It utilizes timeseries specific models to capture energy related patterns.
- **Energy Optimization:** Implements reinforcement learning algorithms for demand-response energy management.
- **Occupant Comfort Measurement:** Uses sensors and human feedback models to increase the efficiency of HVAC systems.
- **Life Cycle Assessment:** Uses life cycle assessment models for the assessment of the environmental impact of buildings

This layer is important for anticipatory decision-making within operations for buildings. The framework enables the deployment and update of AI models an MLflow Model registry [19], thereby providing scala-

Fig. 2. Overview of DATAWiSE Reference Architecture diagram.

bility and efficient model deployment. The introduction of Explainable AI (XAI) techniques make the AI-based decision-making processes transparent and understandable, increasing the user friendliness of the system and user trust.

The *User Interaction Layer* enables easy user access for processed insight by providing visual representations with dashboards, interactive tools, and report generation in several friendly user interfaces. It includes:

- The Lifecycle Data-driven Decision Support (LD2S) toolkit delivers analytical analysis of

lifecycle data and circularity appraisals.

- The Data-driven Building Performance Management (DBPM) toolkit provides monitoring and forecasting dashboards for building performance.

The integration of such a layer enables interaction for technical and non-technical stakeholders with the system. The layer also enables web, enhancing the flexibility of the interactions of the stakeholders.

The *Management and Governance framework* is horizontally applied to all the other layers, ensuring compliance, security, and data integrity. It includes:

- Security Framework: Employs extensive end-to-end encryption, controls for access, and safe authentication processes with the use of Keycloak open-source identity and access management framework [18].
- Data Quality evaluation: Uses automated validation processes to detect data anomalies and assess and quantify the quality of data within DATAWiSE Toolkit.
- IFC Data Dictionary: Standardizes building data semantics for interoperability and publicly open through Building Smart International bSDD [20].
- DATAWiSE Data Model: Standardizes all data exchanged among DATAWiSE components to ensure interoperability.

Collectively, these layers form a cohesive and organized structure that satisfies both user-specified functional and non-functional requirements while also supporting the scalable deployment of emerging technologies. The modular structure ensures flexibility to adapt to changing industry standards and thus promotes continuous improvement in data management and analytics.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The advancement of big data frameworks that are scalable is crucial for the utilization of the full potential of Digital Twin solutions for intelligent buildings. The proposed DATAWiSE architecture successfully addresses the main challenges of heterogeneity of the data, interoperability, scalability, and the need for analysis in real-time by employing a combination of system design approaches. By consolidating disparate data sources, enabling complex data processing tasks to be performed on them, and by applying analytical techniques that leverage the capabilities of artificial intelligence, this architecture forms a solid basis to optimize building management and operating efficiency.

A significant feature of the present study is the structured framework of processing levels that enables the efficient utilization of, aggregation of, storing of, and analysis of the data. With the use of modular and service-oriented analytics, the platform establishes the ability of adaptation with new technologies and the introduction of new data-oriented practices with ease. Finally, the inclusion of XAI enhances transparency for users of different operational areas and expertise.

Despite these achievements, there remain many areas that need to be explored further. To begin with, focus should be placed on ensuring automation of data governance and quality assurance systems to ensure constant reliability and conformity to changing regulatory standards. In addition, applying federated learning methods may promote privacy-aware analytics by ensuring decentralized processing of data without having to store and propagate such information in a centralized way.

Finally, future research should investigate the design of data management systems to build data utilizing new methods such as knowledge graphs. Moreover, the increased complexity of smart buildings supports the use of adaptive learning methods in the analytical model to create the possibility of improved self-optimization of models based on changing patterns and anomalies of building performance. Lastly, increased interoperability in design through dynamic and secure data-sharing platforms will enhance its integration into large smart city networks.

In conclusion, the DATAWiSE architecture provides a secure, scalable, and smart framework that is capable of enabling interoperable data-driven solutions in the smart building field. Its modularity is sufficiently flexible to allow room for growth and evolution in the future, and its focus on security, transparency, and interoperability makes it a critical tool in the further digital transformation of the built environment. By highlighting key research challenges and setting out paths to further improvement, this paper opens the door to the development of smarter, more efficient, and more sustainable smart buildings.

MATCH & CONTRIBUTION

This contribution aligns well with the theme of the ICE IEEE 2025 conference on "AI-driven Industrial Transformation: Digital Leadership in Technology, Engineering, Innovation & Entrepreneurship". The manuscript outlines the design process of the DATAWiSE Reference Architecture, created in the context of a European Union-funded project aiming at the development and testing of building and building portfolio management tools. It outlines a structured approach to identifying user needs in the built environment, translate them into functional and non functional technical requirements and proposes a system architecture design capable of managing demanding big data generated by buildings and hosting AI applications for their energy and non-energy management. Additionally, the research highlights the importance of value creation through improved decision-making processes, enhanced operational efficiency, and increased sustainability—key drivers of the digitalization of the built environment. The modularity of the architecture, as well as the fact that it can support future smart city applications, further increase its applicability and potential impact in real-life contexts.

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. Tao, M. Zhang, Y. Liu, and A. Y. C. Nee, "Digital twin in industry: State-of-the-art," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 2405–2415, 2021.
- [2] L. Klein, H. Wörtche, and N. Weiler, "Iot and big data analytics for smart buildings: A survey," *Building and Environment*, vol. 187, p. 107147, 2020.
- [3] M. Elnour, A. M. Ahmad, S. Abdelkarim, F. Fadli, and K. Naji, "Empowering smart cities with digital twins of buildings: Applications and implementation considerations of data-driven energy modelling in building management," *Building Services Engineering Research & Technology*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 475–498, 2024.
- [4] S. Choenni, M. S. Bargh, T. Busker, and N. Netten, "Data governance in smart cities: Challenges and solution directions," *Journal of Smart Cities and Society*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 31–51, 2022.
- [5] M. R. Bashir, A. Q. Gill, and G. Beydoun, "A reference architecture for iot-enabled smart buildings," *SN computer science*, vol. 3, no. 6, p. 493, 2022.
- [6] Brick Consortium, "Brick Schema: A Uniform Metadata Schema for Buildings," 2025, accessed: 2025-03-01. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/BrickSchema>
- [7] F. M. Dinis, J. Poças Martins, A. S. Guimarães, and B. Rangel, "Bim and semantic enrichment methods and applications: A review of recent developments," *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 879–895, 2022.
- [8] I. M. Putrama and P. Martinek, "Heterogeneous data integration: Challenges and opportunities," *Data in Brief*, p. 110853, 2024.
- [9] E. Sarmas, *Artificial Intelligence for Energy Systems: Driving Intelligent, Flexible and Optimal Energy Management*. Springer Nature.
- [10] DigiBUILD Project, "Digibuild: Digitalisation of the building sector," <https://digibuild-project.eu>, 2023.
- [11] MATRYCS Project, "Matrycs: A modular big data application for energy efficiency in buildings," <https://www.matrycs.eu>, 2023.
- [12] BD4NRG Project, "Bd4nrg: Big data for next generation energy," <https://www.bd4nrg.eu>, 2023.
- [13] H2020 BRIDGE Project, "H2020 bridge: A cooperation initiative between smart grid, energy storage, islands and digitalisation projects," <https://h2020-bridge.eu>, 2023.
- [14] International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), "International data spaces association," <https://internationaldataspaces.org>, 2023.
- [15] GAIA-X European Association for Data and Cloud, "Gaia-x: A federated data infrastructure for europe," <https://www.gaia-x.eu>, 2023.
- [16] FIWARE Foundation, "Fiware: Open source platform for smart solutions," <https://www.fiware.org>, 2023.
- [17] D. Hardt, "The OAuth 2.0 Authorization Framework (RFC 6749)," 2012, accessed: 2025-02-20. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc6749.html>
- [18] Keycloak Developers, "Keycloak - Open Source Identity and Access Management," 2025, accessed: 2025-02-20. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/keycloak>
- [19] MLflow Developers, "MLflow: Open source platform for the machine learning lifecycle," 2025, accessed: 2025-03-01. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/mlflow>
- [20] buildingSMART International, "buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD)," 2025, accessed: 2025-02-15. [Online]. Available: <https://www.buildingsmart.org/users/services/buildingsmart-data-dictionary/>